

POLYMERIZATION SHRINKAGE DISTRIBUTION OF DURING DENTAL RESTORATION OBSERVED BY DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Polymerization shrinkage distribution of composite resins during dental restoration was measured using digital image correlation method. Camera images were monitored during and after the light irradiation. Radial shrinkage strain was to be averagely 0.27% for AP-X and 0.12% for P90 over the whole resin area. Calculated strain results by finite element analysis were lower by 8% ~ 26% than experimental values obtained by digital image correlation. The shrinkage strain occurred much larger in the center part of the resin than in the resin/substrate interface region. The average radial strain of resins on the resin/substrate interface rapidly shrank within 4 minutes, and then converged to a constant value with an increase of time.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dental composite resins undergo a polymerization shrinkage phenomenon during dental restoration. The polymerization shrinkage may lead to interfacial debonding, deflection and reducing the longevity of the restoration. Therefore, the polymerization shrinkage behavior of composite resins is clinically important [1].

By measuring the polymerization shrinkage of composite resin, Iga et al. [2] evaluated the influence of inorganic filler content on polymerization shrinkage using a dilatometer. Feilzer et al. [3] had devised a linometer for relative comparison of polymerization shrinkage. However, these methods could not measure the local deformation distributions of the composite resin.

Digital image correlation (DIC) is a method of calculating the local deformation distributions by comparing images before and after deformation of a structure captured by a digital camera, and it is possible to measure the deformation states of the entire structure [4]. Chuang et al. [5] applied DIC to study the deformation state of dental composite resin after irradiation. Vesna et al. [6] analyzed local shrinkage patterns of a cured dental composite resin using 3D digital image correlation. Furukawa et al. [7] showed that the polymerization shrinkage behaviour of dental composite resin varied with time during irradiation.

In this study, polymerization shrinkage distributions of two types of composite resins, Clearfil AP-X (Kuraray, Japan) and Filtek P90 (3M ESPE, USA), were observed during dental restoration by a DIC method. The measurement of a composite resin shrinkage during the restoration was performed in the process of and after the light irradiation. DIC measurement results and were compared with the results of finite element analysis (FEA).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Dental restoration

Two types of composite resin were used in this study: Clearfil AP-X of methacrylate disposition and Filteck P90 of silorane series. As illustrated in Table 1, polymerization shrinkage of P90 was half

of AP-X, which were provided as trade-marks by each composite resin manufacturer.

A ring type substrate was used to measure polymerization shrinkage behaviours of the composite resins. The ring substrate with 6 mm outer diameter, 4 mm inner diameter and 2 mm height was made of polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA), which was easy to adhere with the dental composite resin. After the ring substrate was cleaned, the adhesive resin was applied to the inner wall of the ring substrate using a micro brush and dried by the air. Light irradiation was conducted for 10 s to partially cure the adhesive layer with an LED irradiator (Morita Pnecure, Japan). The substrate hole was filled up with the composite resin.

Table 1. Dental composites used in this study [8]

Composite	Resin Matrix	Filler	Shrinkage (vol.%)
Clearfil AP-X	Bis-GMA TEDGMA	3 μm Barium glass, Silica particle (85.5 wt%)	1.9
Filtek P90	Silorane	0.01-3.5 μm (average 0.47 μm) quartz particles, yttrium fluoride (76 wt%)	0.88

2.2 Digital image correlation analysis

Fig. 1 shows a schematic of DIC. The deformation is calculated by comparing the photographs before and after deformation based on the random pattern of the material surface [8, 9].

Figure 1. Schematic of digital image correlation method

The prepared specimen was put on a slide glass its surface was and patterned using aqueous paint spray for DIC measurement. As seen in Fig. 2 the LED head was maintained at a distance of 2 mm from the bottom of the specimen during the irradiation. The light irradiation was conducted at an intensity of 1000 W for 20 s. Polymerization shrinkage distribution was measured using the DIC camera system (ARAMIS 2M LT, GOM, Germany).

To look for a proper exposure time during the irradiation, we carried out several time of tests. For Clearfil AP-X, the preceding test was preceding by proceeding 6 steps from 0.20 ms to 0.45 ms in 0.05 ms increment. The proper exposure time was confirmed to be 0.3 ~ 0.4 ms as Fig. 3. In this study, the exposure time during the irradiation was used as 0.3 ms.

For 20 seconds of the irradiation, the shutter speed of the camera was 3 frames / s. After that, the shutter speed was 10 frames / min until 600 s from the initial irradiation. The acquired image was composed of 1624×1236 pixels. The facet size in the image was 17×17 pixels, the facet step was 8×8 pixels, and the facet number was 321×244 .

Figure 2. Schematic of experimental set-up

Figure 3. Photographed images and DIC analysis results as a function of exposure time

2.3 Finite element analysis

FEA using the equivalent elastic modulus obtained in the previous study [10] for polymerization shrinkage at the surface of the specimen was performed and then compared with DIC results. FE model was a quarter of the axisymmetric three-dimensional model. This model mesh was composed of 2280 elements and 7175 nodes. The interfaces among the composite resin, adhesive layer, and outer ring had a complete bonding condition. Mechanical properties of the materials applied to the model are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of dental materials for FEA

	Composite resin		Adhesive layer		Substrate
	Clearfil AP-X	Filtek P90	Clearfil AP-X	Filtek P90	PMMA
Young's modulus (MPa)	188 (equivalent)	157 (equivalent)	4,400	2,100	3,200
Poisson's ratio	0.26	0.3	0.24	0.3	0.3

3 RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Fig. 4 (a) and (b) show the major strain distributions of the composite resin of AP-X and P90, which was measured with the DIC method. The maximum strain occurred just inside the resin/substrate interface. However, strain measurement was impossible on the edge of the resin part due to the

excessive light concentration induced by light reflections on the lateral interface. The shrinkage strain just after 600 s from the start of light irradiation was measured to be averagely 0.27% for AP-X and 0.12% for P90 over the as hole resin area. These values are significantly lower than those (see table 1) provided by the manufacturer. The reasons for the lower average shrinkage strain seemed to originate from the viscoelastic curing process. Initial state of the composite resin was sol state. After irradiation, the composite resin stiffened as it shrank. The shrinkage strain showed non-uniform as shown in Fig. 2, and occurred much more in the center part of the resin than in the resin/substrate interface region. Although such behavior of shrinkage strain distribution for AP-X had similar trends to that of P90, the average strain of P90 was about 40 % of that for AP-X.

Figure 4. Major strain distributions of (a) AP-X and (b) P90 measured by DIC

Calculated strain results by FEA are shown in Table 3. The shrinkage strain of the cured composite resin was 0.11% for P90 and 0.20% for AP-X on the upper surface. FEA results were lower by 8% ~ 26% than experimental values.

Table 3. Comparison of the shrinkage results by DIC method and FEA

Method	DIC		FEA	
	AP-X	P90	AP-X	P90
Average shrinkage strain (%)	0.27	0.12	0.20	0.11

Fig. 5 shows the average radial shrinkage strain behaviors of resin part near the resin/substrate interface as a function of time. The average radial shrinkage strain of AP-X was larger than that of P90. The reasons for the larger shrinkage strain were likely due to the fact that shrinkage of the resin was 2 times higher for AP-X than for P90. The average radial strain of resins on the resin/substrate interface rapidly shrank within 4 minutes. During the light irradiation, the average radial shrinkage strain of AP-X was continuously decreased, but P90 was temporarily positive and then decreased after 13 s. This phenomenon means that the heat by the exothermic polymerization and LED light source influenced more the thermal expansion of P90 than that of AP-X. After finishing the light irradiation, the shrinkage strain for both composite resins (AP-X and P90) converged to a constant value with an increase of time.

Figure 5. Average radial shrinkage strains on the resin/substrate interface

4 CONCLUSION

Through the DIC method, the average shrinkage strain was measured 0.27% for Clearfil AP-X and 0.12% for Filtek P90. Average strain of P90 was about 40 % of that for AP-X. Those values in FEM calculation were lower by 8% ~ 26% than experimental values. The shrinkage strain showed non-uniform, and occurred much more in the center part of resins than in the resin/substrate interface region. Both composite resins (AP-X, P90) demonstrated the tensile shrinkage near the resin/substrate interface. The average radial strain of resins on the resin/substrate interface rapidly shrank within 4 minutes, and then converged to a constant value with an increase of time.

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